

Original Article

Economic Transformations and Rising Divorce Trends in Dir Upper Pakistan

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Abstract

Escalating trends in the number of divorces in traditional societies is a global as well as national concern. This study explores the transforming economic factors causing divorces in the traditional society of Dir. An area once characterized by rigid socio-cultural and religious norms with excessive familial cohesion. A qualitative methodology was adopted where the data was collected from 15 divorced men, 15 divorced women, a family judge, Lawyers, members of local dispute resolution council and religious scholars within the area. Thematic analysis revealed that the transformation in the economic system has led to factors like women economic independence and less dependency over male members cause increase in the number of divorces in the region. The study suggests a culturally sensitive framework for strengthening familial ties and controlling divorces.

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INTRODUCTION

The number of divorces across the world is increasing, and it is creating a serious problem of family stability and social cohesion (Office for National Statistics [ONS], 2021). As an example, the average divorce rate in the United Kingdom was 42, and it had risen by 9.6% over the past year (ONS, 2021). In 2020, Maldives had the highest divorce rate of 5.52 per 1,000 people, then Kazakhstan (4.6), Russia (3.9), Belgium (3.7), and Belarus (3.7) (United Nations, 2020). As of 2018, the rate of divorce in the United States per 1,000 inhabitants was between 2.7 and 2.9 on average annually (United Nations, 2020). In Pakistan, divorce has been on the rise regardless of cultural and religious values that do not encourage divorce (Khattak et al., 2018). In 2019, a survey conducted by Gallup-Gilani, 58% of Pakistanis said the rate of divorce was increasing in the country. This perception is corroborated by official records: 3,800 divorce cases were registered in Karachi in the first quarter of 2020 and 7,568 divorce cases and 439 khula cases in Rawalpindi in January-November 2021 (The News International, 2021). Such statistics suggest that there is an increasing trend towards marital breakdown and litigation in the Pakistani community. Economic changes have become a much-needed factor that affects marriage. The increase in divorce rates both globally and locally has been caused by changes in individual household income, financial autonomy of women, and shifting expectations about the role of women in the economy (Gul, Naz, and Baloch, 2018; Noor, Noreen, and Haq, 2023). These dynamics are further intensified by personal factors like age, education and socioeconomic status, which frequently result in a breakdown of communication and failure to meet the expectations (Gaffal, 2010). Following the growing trends in divorces in the world and in Pakistan, this paper was meant to evaluate the role of changing economic dynamics, that have led to the increasing divorce rates, in the socio-cultural set up of the District Dir, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Knowledge of these dynamics is necessary to create specific interventions that help in strengthening family relations and enhance healthier marital relationships.

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Statement of the Problem

Over the last ten years, the rate of divorce in Pakistan has increased at an alarming rate, which indicates a radical shift in the family structure and societal values (Noor, Noreen, and Haq, 2023). As an example, despite an increase in the number of khula cases in 2014 (16,942) to 2016 (18,901) in Punjab (Ramzan et al., 2018), in 2017, 15,000 cases of divorce were registered in Karachi and 6,000 khula in Lahore (Ferozi, 2017). Equally, according to media reports, in the month of January of 2022 alone, children and women of Rawalpindi issued 11 khula notifications and served 74 divorce notifications at their family courts (The Nation, 2023). Khyber Pakhtunkhwa especially is a worrisome trend because socio-cultural and religious values traditionally focused on family bonds and marital security. This was the case in the past in District Dir Upper, where joint family systems and traditional values have been the order of the day, but today, marital dissolution is increasing at an alarming rate. The initial statistical information obtained in local courts and arbitration centers show that not only the rate of husband-initiated divorces but wife-initiated khulas is skyrocketing during the last ten years.

The District Family Court registered 27 khula cases and 112 divorce cases and Local Disputes Resolution Council registered 13 khula cases and 27 divorce cases in the same year (in-person interview with officials). Economic changes seem to be an important motivator of this tendency. The increased unemployment, inflation, and income insecurity have already become a great burden to households, which often results in marital discord (Ramzan et al., 2018; Envision Pakistan, 2024). Financial dependency on overseas workers in rural communities such as Dir Upper has led to disproportionate financial relations among households, which in some cases leads to conflict in the allocation of available resources and decision making (Adams, 2017). Also, the increasing financial autonomy of women due to education and the availability of jobs has changed the traditional gender role in such a way that women are able to demand khula once marriages are not satisfactory (Malik et al., 2021; Dialogue Pakistan, 2024). Together with the increasing dowry pressure and debts, these shifts have increased marital economic stress (Bloom Pakistan, 2024). It is critical to learn the interdependence of these economic factors with cultural norms in Dir Upper in order to come up with strategies that can empower family systems and minimize divorce cases. This research seeks to address this gap by uncovering the impact of economic changes on the increased divorce rates in District Dir, KP, Pakistan, and thus offer much information to policymakers, practitioners, and community leaders to ensure families stand. Objective of the Study To evaluate the impact of changing economic variables on the higher divorce rates in District Dir, KP, Pakistan.

Study Objective

To determine the impact of changing economic variables in the rise in divorce rates in District Dir, KP, Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY

This research was carried out within the interpretivistic paradigm that solely focuses on understanding social phenomenon through the lens of the participants (Krueger and Neuman, 2006). The qualitative method was used to investigate the causes of divorce among men and women living in Dir Upper, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, a region that is characterized by increasing the divorce rates since the Musharraf regime. Purposive sampling was used to select the participants which comprised of divorced men and women, a family court judge, expert lawyers, religious scholars and members of Disputes Resolution Council. They suggested a sample of thirty divorcees (15 male and 15 female), and the final sample size was determined based on data saturation (Sim, Saunders, Waterfield, and Kingstone, 2018). The primary source of data collection was semi-structured interviews conducted under the guidance of an interview protocol, and the interviewers were female research assistants, trained and instructed to interview women in a manner that fits cultural norms (Holstein and Gubrium, 2004). The transcripts of interviews were analyzed thematically in order to find patterns and ideas about the reasons of divorce (Kuckartz, 2014).

FINDINGS

Economic Autonomy and the Erosion of Patriarchal Power in Marriage

It was traditionally considered that men are the sole breadwinners, and the dependence of women is one of the forms of patriarchal rule in the family. However, with the women beginning to access education, getting employment, becoming more stable financially, the stereotypical types of roles are being put to test, and so the women are modernized and given more independence to be self-reliant. This empowerment has not only altered the household set up but also provided women with means of escaping unhappy marriages. The following sub-themes describe such changes. Respondents emphasized that the relationship in the marriage in Dir Upper has changed due to the empowerment of women in the economy. The gender role of traditional male dominance has been challenged by the concept of financial liberation that has made women have a chance to escape unhappy marriages with the modernization centered on gender equality.

Conventionally, the economic dependency of women favored the concept of their male superiority in the marital relations. It has disrupted this usual power structure, according to the participants, by the women entering the work force and receiving income, in most instances, has created conflict where men do not readily part with power. Historically, it was all dominated by men as women had no source of income.

“Women are currently in employment and earning thereby gaining the confidence to speak out. This was not the case in my case because once I started to make contributions, my husband felt threatened. He wanted to keep things under control, and I did not want to yield to his supremacy. This was a perpetual struggle that resulted in divorce. The reason is that it places women in a disadvantaged position to face the harsh reality of life.” (Divorced Female Participant)

“The rationale is that it leaves women at a disadvantageous place of having to deal with the harsh reality of life. The economic autonomy has transformed the views of women. They cannot bear disrespect anymore as they are aware that they can live without their husbands. This change is beneficial to the rights of women, yet she can also be considered the cause of conflicts in marriage as men are not prepared to share power. What is it that you are asking”? -- (Lawyer, Specialist in Family Affairs)

“What do you want? When I began to earn, I noticed that conventional expectations fall apart. Men experience the fact that their role is threatened and instead of changing with the times, they tend to respond negatively. This strain often culminates in divorce”. — (Judge, Family Court)

The above stories show that monetary autonomy has upset conventional gender orders and power conflicts have emerged in marriages. Although this empowerment is an expression of modernization that focuses on equality, it also disrupts the relationships that are based on patriarchal value, which makes divorce rates increase.

Female Capability to leave unhappy Marriages

The participants highlighted that economic empowerment has availed women with viable ways to abandon marriages that do not deliver to their expectations. In contrast to the olden days when women were more or less held by the economic nature of their existence and thus had to live with abusive or otherwise unhappy relationship, women are currently becoming more autonomous and are pursuing divorce with ease. In old times, women would remain in poor marriages since they had nowhere to go.

“Today, when woman is educated and earning, she realizes that she is able to live on her own. The reason I left my marriage is that I was fed up with the continuous disrespect and I was aware that I could do without it. — (Divorced Female Participant)

“Women are not afraid of divorce these days as they have a financial security. This is a significant shift since in the past, leaving a husband was a social and economic disaster. Today they view divorce as a means of getting back dignity and peace”. — (Religious Scholar)

“Women have been bold enough to make their own decisions due to economic empowerment. Most of the times I have witnessed women take the first step towards divorce due to lack of feeling trapped by financial dependency”. — (DRC Member)

The stories that have been described in this theme highlight a radical change of relationships in marriage due to the empowerment of women economically. Financial autonomy not only has created a threat to traditional male dominance, but has also given women the feasible tool to get out of marriages that are not as per the expectation. This change indicates the importance of modernization on gender equality, and personal autonomy which undermined the marital stability which existed in the past through patriarchal norms. Although empowerment enhances the agency and welfare of women, it is also destabilizing the relationships that are founded on strong gender hierarchies and this is also contributing to the rising divorce rates in Dir Upper. The findings can be aligned with the findings of the Modernization Theory, in accordance with which economic growth and the alteration of the gender roles is the main factor that changes the family composition and dynamics within the family.

Employment Pressures and Work-Life Imbalance as Drivers of Marital Breakdown

The experiences of the participants indicate that some of the stressors that have emerged into marriage relationships in Dir Upper pertain to employment issues. Modernization and economic opportunities have helped in enhancing living standards, but they have also posed some major challenges like work-life imbalance and migration to secure educational and occupational opportunities. The result of these changes is emotional detachment, lack of communication and poor relationship that will eventually cause divorce. Respondents pointed out that hectic work schedules especially in the city places of work eliminate the traditional family practices. The work-related stress and long working hours decrease the time that couples spend together, thus establishing an emotional distance and blowing up.

“My work timetable in a private company became extremely busy when I joined it. I would get home late and leave early and my wife felt that she was neglected. She explained that I was more concerned with my job than our relationship was. We attempted to adapt, but time and communication were always wanting and ultimately destroyed the marriage”. — (Divorced Male Participant)

“Employment has re-assigned priorities. Men and women are too much occupied with making money to the extent that they end up neglecting their relationship. The couples in most instances barely converse as they are too tired to chat after work. Such absence of emotional attachment creates misunderstandings and divorce”. -- (Attorney, Specialist in Family Matters).

“Work-life imbalance is a problem that is on the increase. Individuals believe that the solution is to make more money and this belief frequently leads to the emergence of new issues. Without spending time together, a minor problem can develop into a major argument between partners”. — (Judge, Family Court)

The stories above show that work-life imbalance has emerged to be a major stressor in contemporary marriages. As much as working provides a stable source of income, it also denies one a chance to connect emotionally, which contributes to the marital breakdown in Dir Upper.

Emotional Distance as a result of migration to work

The participants said migration as a cause of seeking employment, either to cities or to other countries, has caused both physical and emotional separation between marital partners. This distance is the cause of loneliness, mistrust and eventual marital dissolution.

“My husband had gone to the Gulf to work shortly after we got married. Initially, I believed it was towards our better future but with time, the distance became too large to deal with. Our communication was minimal and I was all alone. At some point we chose to part ways as the emotional distance was too big”. -- (Divorced Female Participant)

“Migration to work is currently one of the largest causes of divorce. When men leave the country they take years to stay elsewhere and women are left abandoned. They are occasionally infidelity suspects, and the trust is lost. I have witnessed such a number of cases in the court”. — (Judge, Family Court)

“Previously, men used to work in the society and families remained united. Today, through globalization, individuals go to great distances in search of employment. This physical distance breaks emotional bonds and augments the rate of divorce”. — (Religious Scholar)

The above stories have shown that job migration causes a long-term physical distance, which destroys emotional closeness and confidence. This is an indicator of the economic aspect of modernization where the need to achieve financial security at the expense of marital unity is the most common trend. The strain associated with employment to explain the paradox of modernization is that though more opportunities are created in the economy to increase the financial security of the people, it also brings the burden of stress that disrupts marriage relations. Structural changes in family life can be observed in work-life imbalance and migration to employment, which is the claim of the Modernization Theory that economical development changes social norms and relations between individuals.

Materialism and Financial Pressures as Catalysts for Marital Breakdown

Accounts by the participants have shown that materialistic needs and economic demands have become major causes of marital conflict in Dir Upper. The exposure to the city life and modernization has increased the desire of luxury goods, branded clothes, modernizing houses, and regular recreation. These increased demands in most cases surpass the economic ability of the families resulting in discontent and strain in the marriages. Study participants pointed out that this is due to such pressures causing unending arguments on the issue of money, which destroys emotional connections and consequently leads to divorce.

“When we married, my wife desired a way of life in big cities, modern furniture, high cost clothes, and taking out every week. I did my best, yet my earnings were not able to match such expectations. All the discussions were over money and in the end we concluded that we should separate.” — (Divorced Male Participant)

“Media and migration have brought in materialism in our culture. Women are demanding that their husbands afford luxuries that have never featured in our cultures. In the event of failure to meet these expectations, they are unhappy and would divorce”. — (Religious Scholar)

“I can see numerous instances where the expectation of finances turns out to be the source of separation. Couples quarrel on money issues as they desire to live like the urban elites yet they lack the means. This discrepancy leads to tension at all times”.(lawyer, specialist in family matters).

The stories above show that the increased material desires have led to creation of unrealistic expectations in marriages. In cases where couples are unable to meet these requirements due to a financial constraint, they get heartsore and even end up in a divorce.

Financial Disputes in Modern Marriages

According to the respondents, issues of finance, in terms of dowry money, inheritance and contribution at home have become very frequent. These discords are a kind of clash between the traditional and the modern financial burdens, as they cause tension between spouses and families. Even after marriage, my in-laws kept insisting on increased dowry.

“To the extent that I declined, they coerced my man and this was a constant point of contention. It came to a point that there was too much stress and we parted ways. The reason is that most women have not been brought up in an environment that allows them to be independent and empowered to make all decisions in life”.(Divorced Female Participant)

“Marriages are now becoming victims of inheritance disputes. There are property wars in families and this is transferred to the relation of a couple. I have witnessed instances in which the bickering over property between the brothers ends in divorce since the wife is too insecure”. — (Judge, Family Court)

“Now there is a large concern of financial contributions. Earning women feel that they have equal say in the household decision, and they make men feel threatened. This struggle of money and power usually separates”. — (DRC Member)

The above stories bring out the role of financial arguments in marriages where the traditional dowry or modern day demands of equality creates recurrent tension in marriages. These struggles represent the two-sided impact of modernization to revolt against traditional ideals and introduce the new economic burden that endangers the life of marriage. Materialism and monetary needs show how modernization transforms the cultural values where the value of consumerism and status is more significant than the traditional simplistic and survival values. These findings are in line with the Modernization Theory which posits that development and exposure to lifestyles in the world results to ambitions that tend not to be at par with the realities in the region which result in marital instability.

Economic Stress and Unemployment

The family insecurities in Dir Upper have been established to be one of the critical elements basing on the experiences of the respondents that unemployment and financial pressures now form major concerns. Modernization has brought about new opportunities and also, the modernization has created financial strains which most families are struggling to manage.

Unemployment in men, increase in cost of living and economic insecurity usually causes frustration, lack of self-esteem and internal disunity in marriages. These economic challenges have effects on divorce as depicted in the following sub-themes.

Financial butting Heads in Marital Discord.

The participants noted that the perception of financial instability (either through unemployment or an uneven flow of income) has a long-term effect on marital relationships by establishing a stressful atmosphere. This tension usually comes in forms of disagreements about household costs and expectations not followed.

“Everything became different when I lost my job. My wife had begun to talk about money and I was humiliated since I could not sustain the family. Life became difficult with the never-ending quarrels on spending and at some point, we thought it was time to part ways”. — (Divorced Male Participant)

“One of the most popular causes of divorce today is economic stress. Failure by men to earn enough frustrates them and leaves the women insecure. This stress usually culminates into criticism and bickering, which destroys the marriage. "Would you please refer me to a lawyer? -I know one at the Bar--he is a great expert in family matters, and I want him to see me.(Lawyer, Specialist in Family Affairs)

“I do observe numerous instances in which divorce is a result of unemployment. Men become insecure and women grow impatient. Financial insecurity leads to a poisonous atmosphere in which even the minutest problem turns into a major confrontation”. — (Judge, Family Court)

The stories above have revealed that financial instability destroys marital harmony by causing tension and developing lack of trust. This is the economic paradox of modernization where as ambitions are increased, economic realities are not keeping up and the marriage can easily break up.

Male Unemployment and the Collapse of Traditional Gender Roles

According to the participants, male unemployment does not only impact on the household income but also destroys the traditional gender roles, which entails men being the breadwinners. Such loss of status usually leads to mental disturbance and poor relationships. In our society, men are expected to take care of the family.

“My self-esteem was destroyed when I lost my job. My wife began challenging my capabilities, and I was not able to cope with it. This respect loss was even worse than the loss of funds, and it ruined our marriage.” — (Divorced Male Participant)

“The unemployed men would be violent or shy because they are threatened in their jobs. This attribute brings about emotional alienation and quarrels that lead to divorce”. — (Religious Scholar)

“The family structures are transformed due to unemployment. Women who make start to take control and men feel helpless. It may result in a divorce as a result of this power play and honour”. — (DRC Member)

The stories above indicate that gender norms are unstable in regard to the unemployment of men which brings in psychological strain and marital disagreement. The findings can be linked to the modernization theory, which demonstrates that the alteration in the economy challenges the established social roles and, in most cases, causes instability in the family. The economic pressure and joblessness is used to portray the problem of marital relationships and how marital relationships can break because of financial instabilities. Modernization brings up the expectations and reawakening of the gender roles but when the economic circumstances cannot support the modernization, the discord in marriages is bound to happen. This theme justifies the theoretical assertion that economic development, though transformational, can also contribute to the structural tensions that emerge to increase the divorce rates.

Economic Role Differences in Homes

The accounts of participants depict that modernization has to a large extent distorted the economic roles of a household and it has been a challenge to the traditional gender roles in Dir Upper. Historically, men were seen as being lone providers and women as household chores. However, the labour of female and the dual income families, have also placed new demands on the territory of joint financial and family responsibility. This transition can be quite stressful when men become unwilling to renegotiate the roles or because they feel that their power is weakened. These dynamics are represented in the following sub-themes.

Dual Income Families and Sharing Household Chores

Contributors brought out that in the occasions where women are financially empowered, they demand that men should increase their participation in the housework. Nonetheless, opposition to these changes may resort to war and divorce.

“When I joined the workforce, I anticipated my husband to assist me with the domestic duties since I was also making money. But he would not, pretexting that it was unnatural to our customs. This never-ending debate about roles turned life laden with stress and at some point we parted ways”. -- (Divorced Female Participant)

“Dual-income families are quite a norm today, yet men want women to take care of everything at home. Women believe that this is not right and fights begin. I have observed numerous cases when such an imbalance contributes to divorce. Payments made to a lawyer who specializes in family matters are considered legal expenses.” (Lawyer, Expert in Family Affairs)

Payments to an expert in family affairs, which is a lawyer are regarded as legal expenses. Modernization has transformed the female expectations. They desire equality in financial matters as well as domestic responsibilities. Failing to adapt, marriages are harmed by men. — (Judge, Family Court)

The stories above show how the dual-income families defy the traditional gender roles, which brings tensions in cases where men do not share home duties. This conflict is an indication of the role of modernization in the re-conceptualization of the role of marriage.

Men are not comfortable with the women economic participation

According to the participants, other men see the financial independence of women as a threat to their power that makes them insecure and causes friction in the marriages.

“My husband could not accept the fact that I was making more than he. He believed that he lost his respect, and began to act aggressively. This feeling of insecurity ruined our relationship”. -- (Divorced Female Participant)

“In our society, men are brought up as the breadwinners. When women make money, they are challenged and respond in a negative manner. This frequently culminates in divorce”. — (Religious Scholar)

“I have heard instances where husbands do not allow their wives to work as they are afraid of being out of control. When it is insisting of the woman, the marriage disintegrates”. — (DRC Member)

The above narratives indicate that men are not comfortable with women participating in the economy, and thus power struggles in marriages take place. This resistance is the opposition between the traditional patriarchal values and the modernization that is based on gender equality. This change in the economic roles in the households is one of the examples of modernization transforming the structures of families. Although the dual-income families are contributing to a better financial stability, they are also disrupting the traditional gender roles, which eventually results in divorce.

These results coincide with the Modernization Theory that assumes that economic growth and the shifting roles of gender upset the traditional social order, altering the marriage process. According to the thematic analysis, the economic reforms have had a great impact of reformulating the marital dynamics in Dir Upper. The financial independence of women, the pressure of their jobs, materialistic needs, and the shifting role of the woman in the family are the new components of conflict that drive the norms and increase the divorce rates. Such results are consistent with the Modernization Theory, which assumes that economic growth and shifting gender roles will disrupt the existing social order, create individualism and disrupting the traditional family structure.

DISCUSSION

The results indicate that the evolution of economic aspects has been a major factor in the increasing divorce rates in Dir Upper as it transformed the dynamics and challenged the traditional norms of marriage. Economic empowerment of women became an important consideration because not only did financial independence interfere with male dominance, but it also allowed women to leave unhappy or abusive marriages. Pressures connected to employment also worsened relationships as the participants noted that long working hours and work-related stress interfered with family routines and male migration to work caused emotional distance and distrust. Modernization has also contributed to the development of material desires, and thus, increased demands in the lifestyle changes, and finances, which consequently culminated into quarrels about dowry, inheritance, and household payments. Economic strain and joblessness were also cited as other key causes of marital conflict with financial insecurity and male unemployment destroying self-esteem and escalating family feuds. Lastly, the trend of dual-income families required renegotiation of domestic work, which was not popular with many of the men as they saw the economic contribution of women as a threat to the traditional gender roles. Taken together, these results highlight that economic modernization, on the one hand, promotes personal freedom and gender equality, but, on the other hand, it has destabilized traditional families, which fits the claim of the Modernization Theory that structural economic transformations destabilize existing social norms and institutions.

Increasing material desires and changing expectations of marriage were also attributed to urban migration and media exposure. These are in line with Pakistani studies that allude to the growing proportion of divorces with urbanization as a result of lifestyle modifications and lessened communitarian authority (Khan et al., 2019; Tahira et al., 2023). International studies also indicate the same whereby modernization and industrialization would enable individualistic norms that may contradict the traditional norms, resulting in marital instability (Sheykhi, 2020). Also, the tendency toward love marriages and the decreased influence of parents in the choice of a spouse is a manifestation of the general modernization process. On one hand, these changes empower agencies of individuals, on the other hand, they weaken the support structures of families, predisposing marital disintegration (Rubab & Alam, 2022; Thi, 2021). The problem of intergenerational conflicts became another critical factor as young people become more independent, and equality is valued, whereas in older generations, the standards of endurance and family respect remain traditional. This observation is similar to national research reports that report similar conflicts in Pakistani families during cultural transition (Naeem et al., 2023). On the whole, these results affirm that the traditional family system is broken, and the individualism values have become institutionalized by modernization, including urbanization, education, and cultural globalization, re-established the expectations of marriage, and undermined institutional structures.

These dynamics are further enhanced by economic transformations. The empowerment of women financially became one of the paramount issues as they were able to oppose the patriarchal rule as well as leave abusive marriage. Globally, the financial independence of women is always associated with increased divorce rates in communities that are in the process of switching between traditional and modern societies (Corradini and Buccione, 2023; Wang and Schofer, 2018). Although gender equality is achieved through empowerment, structural tensions in patriarchal societies are created, because in most cases men take the economic autonomy of women as an affront to their position as the breadwinners. It was also found out that employment-related stress and work-related migration contributed to marital instability. Participants complained that excessive working hours and workplace stresses interfered with family routines, and diminished emotional intimacy and heightened conflicts. These results are in line with studies conducted on Pakistani dual-earner couples that point to the adverse influence of work-family spillover on marriage satisfaction (Abid et al., 2023). Likewise, the movement of men in search of work, although an economic advantage, tends to cause long-term separation of the spouses and a sense of mistrust, undermining the marital relationship, which has also been reported in South Asian or Middle Eastern environments (Sheykhi, 2020). Another important theme was materialism and the growing financial demands. Modernization and the exposure to world media have increased the desires of the modern lives, and there is conflict over the unmet financial needs, dowry, and inheritance. These results are reminiscent of Pakistani research that points out the financial strains and consumerism principles as primary culprits of marital conflicts (Rubab & Alam, 2022; Mahmood, 2016). Divorce in Dir upper was also indicated to be caused by economic stresses and unemployment. Jobslessness and financial insecurity in men were associated with frustration, loss of self-esteem, and domestic tensions, which is aligned with national-level statistics indicating poverty and fluctuating income as the major contributors to the marital breakages among Pakistanis (Khan et al., 2019; Mahmood, 2016).

CONCLUSION

This paper has discussed how transformation in economic factors has led to an increase in divorce rates in Dir Upper, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The results indicated that the economic modernization has greatly influenced the marital patterns that have challenged the conventional standards, generating structural conflicts. The financial empowerment of women, career pressures, materialistic desires, dowry arguments, jobslessness in men, and financial fights between the spouse made them to become the critical factors behind marital instability. Although modernization leads to equality between the genders and individualism, it also destabilizes the patriarchal system of the family, which confirms the claims of the Modernization Theory that economic development destabilizes the existing social systems. These lessons highlight the importance of culturally sensitive interventions that would balance the process of modernization and family unity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Policy Interventions

- Establish community-based counselling services to deal with marital disputes caused by financial strains.
- Implement financial literacy to couples to cope with expectations and household budgets.

Legal support and Institutional support.

- Empower family courts and Dispute Resolution Councils with qualified mediators to deal with cases of economic disputes.
- Introduce changes in the law that would govern dowry payments and competition over inheritance.

Community Awareness

- Carry out sensitization campaigns on the joint domestic roles in two-family income families.
- Encourage cultural discussions in order to balance the traditional to the modern economic reality.

Employment and Economic stability

- Provide rural areas with employment opportunities to men to alleviate strain on marriage as a result of unemployment.
- Encourage women to work and at the same time promote the distribution of household roles fairly.

LIMITATIONS

- Dir Upper was the only study that was restricted and this might not generalize to other regions.
- Data collection was carried out through interviews and this can be subject to subjectivity.
- Economic factors were given most attention, other forms of social and psychological variables were not delved into.

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

- Comparison between rural and urban to investigate the differences in the economic forces of divorce in the regions.
- Longitudinal study in order to determine the effects of changing gender roles in marital stability in the course of time.
- Quantitative research to determine the statistical power of economic determinants of divorce

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